

Pebane Solar Power Plant Project Financial Analysis

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Executive Summary

This study aimed to analyse the financial feasibility of a solar power plant in Zambézia, Pebane District. The analysis was based on the FINPLAN Tool (Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion).

The results suggest that the project is feasible, the NPV is MZN125 Millions and the IRR is 15% (greater than the discount rate of 10%). The sensitivity analysis suggests that the project is not very sensitive to changes in prices and exchange rates, showing that major changes in variables are needed to jeopardize the viability of the project. However, more attention is needed for O&M costs and climate risks since Pebane is somehow prone to climate shocks due to its close location to the coastal line.

The strategic actions do not compromise the project financial feasibility during its lifetime, can be combined, i.e. if the currency depreciates, the price of electricity can be increased or subsidized by the government.

1. Introduction

Mozambique is one of the countries in the world with huge potential of energy generation, either through renewable or fossil fuels. Despite this enviable potential, Mozambique ranks in the top 20 countries with populations without access to electricity in the world¹. By 2023, only 53.4% of the population had access to electricity².

The disparities in access to electricity are even more evident when analyzed by province, as shown in Figure 1. Zambézia is the province with the lowest electricity access rate.

Figure 1: Electricity access in Mozambique by province

Figure 2: Main Source of Energy in Households- Pebane District

Source: Ministry of Economy and Finance – 2024

Source: National Institute of Statistic, 2012

Besides this, due to the precarious connections and the lack of liability system of transport and distribution of electricity in Zambézia, the province has suffered constant power cuts. Constructing a power plant is one of the solutions to improve system liability and productivity, and solve basic problems related to education and health.

This study aims to analyse the financial feasibility of a solar Power plant in Zambézia, Pebane District. Pebane was selected because of its strategic geographical location with access to the sea and where agricultural and mining activities are carried out. In addition, INE's latest District Profile Report, published in 2012, mentions that only 0.7% have access to electricity, most of which is based on the use of kerosene and firewood for lighting.

¹ Tracking SDG7 – The Energy Progress Report 2023. IEA. IRENA. United Nations Statistics Division. The World Bank. World Health Organization

² Ministério de Economia e Finanças - Balanço do Plano Económico Social e Orçamento do Estado 2023 - Mozambique

2. Methodology

The financial analysis was based on the FINPLAN Tool (Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion), from the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). To model the analysis, was used a plenty of data resources in Mozambique, which involved technical (Electricidade de Mozambique), economic and financing data (Bank of Mozambique).

Table 1: General Data to Model FINPLAN

Financial Inputs		Technical Inputs	
Electricity Price (MZN/kWh)	6	Technology	Solar
Investments (Millions USD)	17	Generation Capacity (MW)	25
Loan (Millions USD)	10	Annual production (GWh)	40
Equity (Millions USD)	7	Lifetime (Years)	25
O&M Costs (Millions USD)	0.5	Construction Period (Years)	3
Discount Rate	10%		
Inflation Rate (MZN)	3.3%		
Corporate Tax	32%		
Exchange Rate (USD/MZN) – steady e	64		

In addition, assumptions have been made to model the project:

Table 2: Assumptions to Model FINPLAN

Items	Assumptions
Interest Option	Constant
Depreciation	Linear for 25 years
Spread for short term deposits (%) above local inflation	-1%
Spread for stand-by facility (%) above local inflation	3.5%
Shareholders Return	
<i>Approximate average return</i>	8
<i>Disposal year</i>	2029
<i>Discount rate</i>	7

To assess the sensitiveness of the project, 4 variables was considered and modelled in the FINPLAN. The scenarios were built to see how changes in electricity price, exchange rate, Power plants risks-Climate risk and Operations and Maintenance Costs affects the NPV, IRR, Dividends, Loans Outstanding, the Break Even Point and Revenues.

Table 3: Sensitivity Data Analysis

Electricity Price	%_ BAU	MZN/kWh	O&M Cost	%_ Total Cost	USD
Optimistic	More 10%	6.6	Optimistic	Less 2%	0.3
BAU		6	BAU	3%	0.5
Medium	Less 10%	5.4	Medium	More 5%	0.9
Worse 1	Less 15%	5.1	Worse	More 10%	1.7
Worse 2	Less 50%	3			
Exchange Rate	% BAU	MZN/kWh	Power Plants Risks	% BAU	Production (GWh)
Optimistic	Less 5%	60.8	BAU	100%	40
BAU		64	Medium 1	95%	38
Medium	More 10%	70.4	Medium 2	90%	36
Worse 1	More 15%	80	Worse 1	85%	34
Worse 2	More 50%	83.2	Worse 2	75%	30

3. Results

From the basic scenario, Business as Usual (BAU), the results indicate that the project is financially feasible, where the NPV is MZN125 Millions and the IRR is 15%. In average, during the lifetime of the project, the investors would receive MZN180.6 Million.

Next, the results are presented to demonstrate how financially sensible this project is to changes in 4 different variables. The financial indicators in consideration are: NPV, IRR, Dividends, Loans Outstanding, the Break Even Point and Revenues.

Electricity Price

To analyse the sensitivity of the project to price changes, the main indicator considered was Dividends. Of the different prices adopted, it was found that the price of electricity must be higher of 5.1 MZN/kWh, because below that, IRR tends to be smaller than 10% (discount rate) and dividends will also be reduced, as indicated by the figures 3 and 4. The most critical case is when electricity prices are reduced by 50% of BAU, where the investors do not receive dividends during the debt repayment period (2026 to 2031).

Figure 3: Project feasibility indicators

Figure 4: Dividends (Millions MZN)

Exchange Rate

Loans Outstanding variable was considered to analyse the sensitivity of the project to changes in the exchange rate. The value of the loan begins to decrease from 2026, as this is the year when the debt repayments begin. However, the more the Metical depreciates, the higher the obligations become, as shown in figure 5, and this has a negative impact on the viability of the project. For example, when the exchange rate is 83.2, the project becomes unfeasible because the IRR is 8%, and if the exchange rate is 60.8 MZN means the Metical appreciated and the project is more feasible.

Figure 5: Project feasibility indicators

Figure 6: Loans Outstanding (Millions MZN)

Operations and Maintenance

The cost of O&M can change depending on various factors, such as the cost of qualified maintenance personnel, the cost of importing or buying the materials (solar panels) needed, among others. To analyse the variability of O&M costs, was considered the Break-even point financial ratio, once it provides a good insight in case of changes in the costs. As the figures show, O&M costs must not exceed more than 5% of the total cost, as this could make the project unviable. The more the O&M costs increase, the break-even point becomes greater than 1. This means that the solar plant is not generating enough sales to cover its electricity generation costs. Note that the Break Even-Point sharply reduces from 2032, since 2031 is the last year where the repayments costs are paid.

Figure 7: Project feasibility Indicators

Figure 8: Break Even Point

Power Plant Risk

The operation of the solar power plant can be affected by different risk and makes it not generates electricity in 100% of total capacity. Some of this can be the reduced solar irradiation, climate shocks that can destroy totally or partially the power plant as well as the negative human action on destroying the infrastructure. In this case, operating below 90% of the power plant capacity, means generating less revenues to make the project feasible (see figures 9 and 10).

Figure 9: Project Feasibility Indicators

Figure 10: Revenues (Millions MZN)

5. Discussion

In Mozambique the price of electricity has more flexible control by the company and the Government. The opposite scenario happens with the Exchange rate and climate risks.

Since Mozambique is an Open Economy and his Trade Balance is negative (imports more than exports), exchange rate volatility can be high depending on the level of external shocks. Despite this, the scenarios indicate that it would take major shocks to the economy for the exchange rate to depreciate to a level that compromises the viability of the project. In other words, the Metical would have to depreciate by more than 20% for the project to be unviable.

In the case of climatic risks, Mozambique is very prone to shocks since it is entirely bathed by the coast. The district of Pebane in particular is located near to the coastal zone and was one of the districts affected by Cyclone IDAI in 2019³. Although, Pebane have good potential for solar power generation and it can operate with more than 90% of its capacity.

The O&M costs is under the control of the company but, once most of the material need for the maintenance is imported, it can vary in case the currency depreciate. Besides that, globally the LCOE of solar generation is decreasing and during the project lifetime, Mozambique is also planning to install some panel companies' producers, since there considerable critical mining extracted in Mozambique.

³ Government of Mozambique. 2019. Tropical Cyclone IDAI and Kenneth in Mozambique – National Situation Report - National Health Institute. World Health Organization

Strategic actions do not compromise the project financial feasibility during its lifetime, can be combined, i.e. if, for example, the currency depreciates during the debt repayment phase, the price of electricity can be increased by, for example, 1 metical, or depending on the macroeconomic situation, can be subsidized by the government.

In general, these are the many aspects to bear in mind, during the project lifecycle:

- (i) **Company level:** Keep an eye on the market for O&M costs, making sure they don't exceed USD 0.9 million and develop a contingency plan for the use of funds to avoid high losses in case of climate shocks.
- (ii) **Government Level:** Adopt market control policies to guarantee stable electricity prices and control the exchange rate to be below 75 MZN per USD so as not to jeopardize the feasibility of the project, due to the increase on loans payments.

Once part of Pebane is located in coastal line, could also be developed a feasibility study of installing a wind power plant which could generate less intermittent electricity that can be used in industrial and transformation sector on processing minerals.

6. Conclusion

This study aimed to analyse the financial feasibility to install a solar Power plant in Zambézia, Pebane District, using FINPLAN tool. In general, the project is not very sensitive to changes in prices and exchange rates, showing that major changes in variables are needed to jeopardize the viability of the project. This shows that install a solar power plant in Pebane can be financially feasible, although a special attention must be given to O&M costs and develop a contingency plan to minimize the climate risk, since from the taken analysis, its revealed to be financially sensible.

7. References

1. Electricidade de Mozambique. Feasibility Study for the 220kV Interconnection Namialo-Metoro. Byucksan Power.
2. Instituto Nacional de Estatística. (2012). Estatísticas do Distrito de Pebane
3. Government of Mozambique. (2019). Tropical Cyclone IDAI and Kenneth in Mozambique – National Situation Report 3. National Health Institute. World Health Organization
4. Ministério de Economia e Finanças - Balanço do Plano Económico Social e Orçamento do Estado 2023 – Mozambique
5. Tracking SDG7 – The Energy Progress Report 2023. IEA. IRENA. United Nations Statistics Division. The World Bank. World Health Organization
<https://www.bancomoc.mz/>

